

SOLVING AN ASSIGNMENT PROBLEM UNDER LINGUISTIC VALUATIONS WITH GENETIC ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Staff selection for the varying activities performed by enterprises requires a coherent approach, which cannot be simplistic, to the information held. The use of flexible computation and the vague representation of knowledge available by means of natural linguistic labels allows the problem to be recognised as it is in real life. This paper is an attempt to supply a satisfactory solution to a real staff management problem with linguistic information using genetic algorithms.

KEY WORDS: Staff selection, relationships between jobs, linguistic labels, fuzzy numbers, genetic algorithms.

1. INTRODUCTION

The hiring of new staff and the assignment of current staff to specific tasks constitute a crucial decision, since the very survival of the enterprise can depend upon an appropriate choice being made. This is true in all areas of the economy, but is even more so in those in which turbulent trading conditions or cut-throat competition in the business make it vital to have personnel with sufficient flexibility and adaptability. In these circumstances correct choice of staff has a yet greater influence over future development of the company.

The aim of this paper is to attempt to devise a model for staff selection in conditions of uncertainty, such that it will both reduce to a minimum the risks arising from performance of tasks by unsuitable personnel and maximise the capacity of the firm by means of optimal assignment of workers. This model will allow incorporation of all information which may be to hand, however ambiguous or subjective it may be, and cope with the lack of precision that is a concomitant of this sort of decision making process.

From the point of view of the business, the problem as described is essentially one of optimisation of one relationship: the efficiency of labour and the costs arising from its use. Nevertheless, no company, when choosing the best candidates for a post, can avoid the fact that workers interact with one another and do not perform their duties in isolation. This gives rise to the idea of forming teams able to carry out the work allocated, even if all their members are not of great ability or possessors of a range of skills.

Thus, if the best possible value is to be got from staff selection, this must not merely consider the job profile and the requirements of each of the tasks to be performed in the job, in comparison with the capacities of the candidates. It should also address the personalities of the candidates, because if they are chosen they will belong to a team made up of people with whom they must get along in order to achieve a common goal.

An attempt to collect and evaluate all this information arouses interest in the possible application here of the theory of fuzzy groups [ZADEH, 1965; KAUFMANN

AND GIL-ALUJA, 1990] with the aim of being able to handle suitably the uncertainty which is characteristic of the decision-making processes in staff selection. This paper specifically proposes the use of linguistic labels to represent the information on these variables and lead to a decision-making model which is able to handle such information.

In this respect, it is clear that personnel managers and others charged with determining the standards attained by each candidate in the skills needed for the job prefer to use natural language for this, whatever the tests used (aptitude tests, personality questionnaires, role-plays evaluation workshops, interviews and others). This is because it is quite divorced from reality to express these standards in terms of strict numerical values [STRAUSS AND SAYLES, 1981]. Using normal language may lead to the loss of the precision that numbers can give, but there is a positive counterpart in greater closeness to the problem.

However, to optimise the assignment or selection envisaged, there is a need for some tool able to grasp all the complexity which vague information brings with it, as is also the case if the decision-maker is to reach a good solution [LÓPEZ-GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1995a; LÓPEZ-GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1995b; LÓPEZ-GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1995c]. Thus, for the purposes of this paper it has been decided to use a genetic algorithm. The reason for this is that it is a heuristic method of searching solutions and so does not impose restrictions upon the posing of a problem, however complex it may be. In this study, the algorithm is characterised by its use of a fitting function which allows the evaluation of linguistic information, which is a clear innovation both by way of the novelty of the means used in aiding decision making and because of the contribution regarding treatment with fuzzy technology of the genetic algorithm being put forward.

In the light of the above, the next section will offer a descriptive analysis of the material aims of the work and the modelling proposed. Thereafter the genetic algorithm designed to achieve a good solution to the problem will be presented. Next, there will be an example of the experimental work and discussion of the results obtained. The final section includes the conclusions reached and future developments suggested by the authors.

2. STAFF SELECTION IN AN ATMOSPHERE OF UNCERTAINTY DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS AND MODELLING OF THE PROBLEM

2.1 Choice of Staff

For the purposes of this paper, it will be assumed that the selection of staff consists of choosing a person for a job with a given profile, which may be defined by a set of measurements or values which can then be compared with any candidate's capacities.

In any case, by their very nature the schemes used in selecting staff are affected by a certain dose of subjectivity, and take the form of a succession of stages, during which candidates seen as less suitable are successively eliminated, while an attempt is simultaneously made to grasp what capacities those who are most suited to performing the tasks defining the job will have.

The phases to be completed as selection takes place may be summarised for guidance as the three following [STRAUSS AND SAYLES, 1981, GIL-ALUJA, 1996; DE ANSORENA, 1996]:

1. Establishing a Profile for the Post. This is done by means of an analysis of the tasks to be assigned and possible objectives to be attained. The profile also includes a list of the skills that the candidate must possess in order to carry out the activities involved in the job correctly, together with indications of the weight that each skill has in the specific post concerned.

In practice it is usual to set up a list of all the necessary skills, with these being understood as meaning an essential characteristic of any individual who can do the work efficiently or better. This definition would include all the abilities, personal characteristics, motivations and other features such as self-image, social standing, knowledge the individual has, and so forth. Thus, the activities required by the job in question and the conditions under which duties must be performed may be scrutinised.

Traditionally, certain values have been used to fix the skills needed for a job. Nonetheless, it is obvious that for most of them the degree of compliance does not have

to be rigid, and therefore modelling by means of normal linguistic variables can find an interesting application here.

Further, in establishing the post profile, it is necessary to include relationships with other staff, since organisations are not made up of people carrying out their work in isolation but rather interacting with one another. So, it may be more urgent to get a "good team" rather than "good individuals".

In addition, if it is a question of selecting staff for several posts, then those jobs which are of greatest importance to the management of the firm should be weighted in some manner, as these are the ones which should be most effectively matched to the ideal candidates.

2. Candidate Evaluation. There is an extensive range of choices in respect of the tests that can be used (forms, interviews, examination, tests and so on) [STRAUSS AND SAYLES, 1981; DE ANSORENA, 1996]. All try in one way or another to determine the level of aptitude of a person in respect of specific capacities that are deemed needful in order to perform the duties of a post correctly. However, it is also advisable to keep in mind not just the requirements for the post but also the conditions surrounding it, and especially those concerning the team of staff into which the holder must be incorporated.

It is during this phase that analysis of potential interactions between individuals comes into full play. The reason is that when tasks or jobs in which there is person-to-person contact or which are performed by teams are considered, it is essential to ensure that the workers involved co-operate, that is, that they are compatible when it comes to carrying out their joint work.

This justifies looking into the possible relationships between tasks, and into the level of compatibility between individuals, during the selection process. Such considerations are often made in a subjective way, so that the use of linguistic labels would allow greater closeness to the realities of the decision-making procedure being investigated.

3. Match of Candidate to Profile. Once the degree to which each candidate has a given ability is established, this is compared to the capacities stated in the profile set up for the job in question. This shows how far each candidate matches up to them, and allows an order of preference among candidates to be drawn up, though not without taking into account inter-personal compatibility, which is an objective in parallel with the good match of candidates to posts.

2.2 Fuzzy-linguistic Model for Staff Selection

The model proposed here consists of the following phases:

1. Step one is to determine for what posts staff are to be recruited or to which posts existing staff are to be assigned.

Each post has associated with it known skills requirements,

together with the weighting that each requirement has for the various posts.

Normally, in a quantitative situation this information is expressed as numerical values. However, when working in qualitative areas such as personnel management, which are characterised by vague or imprecise knowledge, the information cannot be set out in a precise numerical way. Thus, it would be a more realistic approach to use linguistic information instead of numbers, provided that the variables involved in the problem lend themselves to expression in this manner [DELGADO *et al.*, 1993]. This way of looking at things can be applied to a wide range of problems, since it allows

information to be represented in a more suitable fashion [YAGER, 1992; HERRERA *et al.*, 1995].

This paper supports the possibility of establishing in linguistic terms information relating to the weighting of the skills needed. It would appear clear that a personnel management expert might not know in a precise numerical way what the weighting for a skill is, but could indicate it in normal linguistic terms. To estimate weightings, and indeed other features, it has been chosen to use a set of nine linguistic LABELS [BONISSONE AND DECKER, 1986], which are as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Thus, for the feature weighting the labels and the trapezoidal fuzzy numbers associated with them that are proposed are the following:

<i>Essential</i>	$(1, 1, 1, 1)$
<i>Extremely High</i>	$(.93, .98, .99, 1)$
<i>Very High</i>	$(.72, .78, .92, .97)$
<i>Fairly High</i>	$(.58, .63, .80, .86)$
<i>Moderate</i>	$(.32, .41, .58, .63)$
<i>Fairly Low</i>	$(.17, .22, .36, .42)$
<i>Very Low</i>	$(.04, .1, .18, .23)$
<i>Extremely Low</i>	$(0, .01, .02, .07)$

Unnecessary

(0, 0, 0, 0)

In addition, when staff are being selected for several posts, the expert or decision-maker may consider that not all of the positions have the same weighting, and prefer solutions aimed at putting the most suitable people into the most crucial posts. For this reason, a label associated with each position must be included to show the weighting that the position has for the recruitment procedure which is under way. This characteristic is defined in this paper in exactly the same way as skill requirements, that is, with nine labels.

Moreover, since the jobs are not independent of one another, the links between them should be analysed, as also the weighting of such links. Here, too, the use of nine labels is felt appropriate.

2. Once the posts have been characterised, the candidates are considered, . Information relating to them includes both the operational levels which they demonstrate in the varying skills needed for the positions,

and the relationships linking individuals with one another:

The two types of information are recorded in the form of nine labels, as in previous details, indicating both levels and relationships, thus:

<u>LEVEL</u>	<u>RELATIONSHIP</u>
<i>Optimum</i>	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>Very High</i>	<i>Very Good</i>
<i>Fairly High</i>	<i>Fairly good</i>
<i>High</i>	<i>Good</i>
<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Indifferent</i>
<i>Low</i>	<i>Bad</i>
<i>Fairly Low</i>	<i>Fairly Bad</i>
<i>Very Low</i>	<i>Very Bad</i>
<i>Lowest</i>	<i>Vile</i>

Using this approach, it comes down to a problem of optimisation using imprecise information and having two aims: good levels in the skills needed for the posts on the part of candidates and good relationships between candidates for linked posts.

3. For evaluate the solutions we propose a model that uses the semantic of fuzzy numbers representing the linguistic labels.

Let x a solution be randomly generated for a problem with n posts. For each post there are m_2 skills which define it, with m_2 degrees of importance for each skill. Thus, to assess the suitability of each person for each post a link must be established between the level the person has of a given skill and the weight assigned to that skill for the job. To achieve this, the proposal is to multiply each fuzzy number associated with the weighting of each skill by the fuzzy number attributed to the level that the person has in that skill, then add up the results of this multiplication [KAUFMANN AND GIL-ALUJA, 1990].

By taking the steps outlined above, it is possible to obtain a fuzzy number setting a value on the ability of each candidate relative to each post. However, the intention is to give an overall value covering the suitability of candidates to posts that will include the fact that the various posts are themselves of different levels of importance. In view of

this, it is proposed that the fuzzy figures for the skills of each candidate should be multiplied by the importance assigned to each post, then add them up, so that the solution as to suitability for posts may be obtained in the form of a fuzzy number.

Nevertheless, the goodness of the solutions will also be determined by the relationships between the candidates included in them. On the one hand, the connections between posts are known, as is the weighting for each, and on the other the relationships between candidates are known. So, a link is established for each post between the weighting of its connections to other posts and the degree of relationship that the candidate allocated to the post has with candidates for related posts. To achieve this, the proposed method would be to multiply the fuzzy numbers associated with the weighting of a link between one post and the others by the level of relationship that the person in the post has with the people assigned to related posts.

Once this has been done, a fuzzy number setting a value on the relationships between each candidate and the rest can be obtained. To set a value on the overall solution, the proposal is to add up all the relationships between all the candidates involved in it.

Finally, the intention is to add the level of skill to the degree of relationship of the solution, so as to get a single value for the goodness of selection of staff that the solution represents. In this phase the personnel manager's preferences must be taken into account, in so far as more weight might be assigned to candidates' suitability for posts or to candidates' ability to work well as a team.

3. GENETIC ALGORITHMS FOR ASSIGNMENT PROBLEMS UNDER LINGUISTIC VALUATIONS

Genetic algorithms are adaptive searching and optimisation tools based on the mechanisms of natural selection and genetics [HOLLAND, 1965, GOLDBERG, 1989; DAVIS, 1991; KOZA, 1994; HERRERA AND VERDEGAY, 1996]. Although many variants are possible, the fundamental rules under which they function are, to operate on a population of individuals (feasible solutions for a problem) which is normally

randomly generated and to change the individuals on each iteration by reference to the following four steps:

1. Evaluation of individuals in the population.
2. Selection of a new set of individuals.
3. Reproduction based on relative suitability or adaptation.
4. Recombination to form a new population by crossover and mutation.

The individuals resulting from these operations form the next population, with iteration of the process until the system presents no improvement possibilities.

As they are simple, easily handled, with few restrictions and good generalisability, these algorithms have been successfully applied to a wide range of problems [LUKASIUS AND KATEMAN, 1989; SANDGREN AND JENSEN, 1990; DEB, 1991; BIETTHAHN AND NISSEN, 1995].

In this paper the genetic algorithm proposed has as its principal characteristic real codification of the solutions. Chains of candidates are generated of the same size as the number of posts available. Two types of problems are distinguished: assignment, in which the number of posts is the same as the number of candidates, and selections in which the number of candidates is greater than the number of posts.

An example of a solution for a case of five posts with five candidates available to fill them (assignment) would be:

$$S_1 = \{2, 4, 1, 3, 5\}$$

This solution indicates that candidate no. 2 comes in the first place and is assigned the first job, no. 4 comes in second place and gets the second job, no. 1 gets job 3, no. 3 gets job 4, and no. 5 job 5.

Once the coding has been decided upon, a battery of these solutions is generated by random processes.

3.1 Suitability or fitness function

To work out the suitability of solutions, the fuzzy evaluation model described in the previous section is used. From this a fuzzy number is obtained as an indicator of the goodness of each solution. To set up a hierarchy among them, the proposal is to use the fuzzy distance [KAUFMANN AND GIL-ALUJA, 1990] each one is from the origin (singleton 0).

3.2 Selection of parents

The next step is the selection, by means of a Roulette Selection Ranking [DAVIS, 1991] of the most suitable individuals, which will become the parents of the next generation, as shown in Figure 2.

					Distance	Accumulated distance	Random numbers between 1 y 24					
2	3	5	4	1	7	7	13	2	5	5	3	1
1	2	2	4	1	3	10	20	3	3	2	4	5
2	5	5	3	1	4	14	17	3	3	2	4	5
4	2	4	4	2	1	15	6	2	3	5	4	1
3	3	2	4	5	9	24	23	3	3	2	4	5

Selection Ranking

Figure 2.

3.3 Crossover

Traditional crossover (single point, uniform, and so on) cannot be used for cross from the parents, because these are an ordered decimal list, assignment of individuals to tasks having been done as a function of the place they occupy in the solution chain.

Thus, the option taken is the use of Cycle Crossover [GOLDBERG, 1989], which conforms with the need for the solutions generated by it to continue to be feasible responses to the problem.

The functioning of this method may be described as follows. After the selection process, there are two parents:

$$S_1 = \{1, 4, 5, 3, 2\}$$

$$S_2 = \{3, 2, 1, 5, 4\}$$

A start is made by taking a post at random (for instance, the first). This is maintained in the next generation, and the process yields:

$$S'_1 = \{1, \quad , \quad , \quad \}$$

$$S'_2 = \{3, \quad , \quad , \quad \}$$

Since the individual occupying the first place in the second chromosome is no. 3, no 3. is sought in the first and is placed, leaving the post the same, thus:

$$S'_1 = \{1, \quad , \quad , 3, \quad \}$$

$$S'_2 = \{3, \quad , \quad , 5, \quad \}$$

The individual holding the fourth position in the second chain, which is the position held by no. 3 in the first, is no. 5. So, this individual is sought in the first chain and placed leaving the position the same.

$$S'_1 = \{1, \quad , 5, 3, \quad \}$$

$$S'_2 = \{3, \quad , 1, 5, \quad \}$$

Now, the individual occupying the third place in the second chain is no. 1. As this individual has already been assigned, a cycle of crossing can now be said to have been completed, and the remaining individuals are dealt with by exchanging the chains. The result is this:

$$S'_1 = \{1, 2, 5, 3, 4\}$$

$$S'_2 = \{3, 4, 1, 5, 2\}$$

3.4 Mutation

The intention of this operator is to add diversity to the solutions. Thus, the intention is to distinguish two types of problem. When it is a question of staff assignment, mutation is between places in the chain. However, when it is a question of selection of staff, there is a random choice made by the model between this form of mutation and a mutation which involves bringing in individuals not contained in the chain.

3.5 Halt criteria for the best solution search

The proposal is for the algorithm to go through a number of generations specified by the user until the best solution is found. Moreover, in order not to lose good solutions, the characteristic termed élitism [GOLDBERG, 1989] has been introduced. This procedure consists of keeping the best individual from a population in successive generations unless and until some other individual succeeds in doing better in respect of suitability. In this way, the best solution for a previous population is not lost until outclassed by a more suitable solution, as may be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3

As explained, application of the model proposed here allows a staff selection process to be carried out under conditions of uncertainty. It takes into account possible links between jobs and the co-operation or lack of it that would ensue among staff members involved. As a form of summary, Figure 4 lays out indications of all the steps described above.

Figure 4

4. EXPERIMENT: AN EXAMPLE OF A PRACTICAL APPLICATION

To check the working of the genetic algorithm, an operational model was developed. Several examples were tried out, including the one described below. This deals with the choice of staff for a branch office of a banking institution. In this way, an attempt was made to demonstrate the usefulness the model being proposed in this paper could have for real problems from the business world.

4.1 Introduction to the problem

Let it be imagined that a banking firm wishes to open a new branch. The first step is to determine which posts are to be filled, and what status in terms of urgency each is to have in relation to the selection process. Thus, we might have:

<i>Post 1: BRANCH MANAGER</i>	<i>Status: Essential</i>
<i>Post 2: SUPERVISOR</i>	<i>Status: Fairly High</i>
<i>Post 3: ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER</i>	<i>Status: Moderate</i>
<i>Post 4: ADMINISTRATIVE CLERK</i>	<i>Status: Low</i>
<i>Post 5: COUNTER CLERK / TELLER</i>	<i>Status: Very Low</i>

For each post, thanks to a number of studies, the skills which must be developed and the weighting that each has for the position in question are known:

Position 1: BRANCH MANAGER

Directing	Weighting: Essential
Authorising/delegating	Weighting: Fairly High
Integrity	Weighting: Moderate
Fixing objectives	Weighting: High
Strategic vision	Weighting: Fairly High

Position 2: SUPERVISOR

Collecting information	Weighting: Low
Analysing problems	Weighting: High
Checking on management procedures	Weighting: Fairly High
Multitasking	Weighting: Very High
Knowledge of the organisation	Weighting: Moderate
Mathematical ability	Weighting: Moderate

Position 3: ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER

Team work	Weighting: Moderate
Flexibility	Weighting: High
Collecting information	Weighting: Very High
Multitasking	Weighting: Fairly Low
Specialisation	Weighting: Fairly High

Position 4: ADMINISTRATIVE CLERK

Business orientation	Weighting: Moderate
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Candidate 4 *C.4*

Candidate 5 *C.5*

Candidate 6 *C.6*

Candidate 7 *C.7*

Candidate 8 *C.8*

For each one it is necessary to find out by some appropriate means the levels in each of the skills required for the posts, as shown in Chart 2.

	C. 1	C. 2	C. 3	C. 4	C. 5	C. 6	C. 7	C. 8
Directing	Very High	Very high	Low	High	High	High	Fairly High	Very High
Authorising	Fairly High	Fairly High	Moderate	Fairly High	Fairly High	Moderate	Moderate	High
Team Work	Moderate	Fairly High	Moderate	Fairly Low	Low	High	Moderate	Fairly High
Flexibility	High	High	Fairly Low	Low	Fairly High	Low	Low	Moderate
Integrity	High	High	Low	Moderate	Fairly Low	Fairly High	Moderate	Fairly High
Collecting Information	Very Low	Moderate	Moderate	Fairly Low	Lowest	High	Fairly Low	Lowest
Analysing Problems	Fairly High	Fairly High	Low	High	Moderate	Fairly High	High	Very High
Fixing Objectives	Very High	Very High	Moderate	High	Fairly Low	Very High	Fairly High	Fairly High
Checking on Procedures	High	High	Low	Moderate	Very Low	Fairly High	High	Low
Multitasking	High	High	Moderate	Fairly High	Low	Fairly High	Low	Fairly High
Knowledge of the Organisation	Low	Fairly High	Moderate	Moderate	Very Low	Moderate	Low	Fairly Low
Strategic Vision	Fairly High	Fairly High	Low	High	Lowest	High	Fairly Low	Very High

Specialisation	Very Low	Moderate	Moderate	Fairly Low	Lowest	Fairly High	Low	Lowest
Comercial Orientation	Lowest	Low	Low	Low	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Personal Charm	Very Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Fairly High	Very High	Lowest	Low
Spoken Communication	Very Low	Fairly High	Low	Very Low	Fairly Low	High	Moderate	Low
Customer Orientation	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	High	Fairly High	Fairly Low	Very Low
Mathematical Ability	Fairly Low	Fairly Low	High	Low	Very High	Moderate	Lowest	High

Chart 2

Finally, as there are links between the posts, the candidates must be looked at [DE ANSORENA, 1996] in order to find out the relationships that there would be between them, as shown in Chart 3.

	C 1	C 2	C 3	C 4	C 5	C 6	C 7	C 8
C. 1	-	Very Good	Bad	Good	Moderate	Very Bad	Moderate	Fairly Bad
C. 2	Very Bad	-	Bad	Moderate	Moderate	Good	Moderate	Very Bad
C. 3	ery Good	Fairly Good	-	Bad	Good	Moderate	Good	Bad
C. 4	Very Bad	Good	Moderate	-	Bad	Good	Moderate	Moderate
C. 5	ery Good	Good	Good	Bad	-	Good	Fairly Bad	Very Bad
C. 6	ery Good	Good	Moderate	Bad	Good	-	Moderate	Bad
C. 7	Bad	Good	Good	Fairly Good	Very Good	Fairly Good	-	Fairly Bad
C. 8	Bad	Fairly Good	Good	Very Good	Moderate	Fairly Good	Moderate	-

Chart 3

For the purposes of application of the operational model, the parameters used in finding the solution by means of the model proposed were:

- Number of generations: 50
- Number of individuals: 100
- Crossover probability: 50 %
- Mutation probability: 30 %

It should be pointed out that the use of a high mutation probability was motivated by the need to bring new individuals into the chains, since if this were not so all that would be obtained would be the best combination of those initially considered who got past the first selections.

In the practical example analysed the final solution obtained was:

<i>Post 1: BRANCH MANAGER</i>	<i>Candidate: C. 8</i>
<i>Post 2: SUPERVISOR</i>	<i>Candidate: C. 6</i>
<i>Post 3: ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER</i>	<i>Candidate: C. 2</i>
<i>Post 4: ADMINISTRATIVE CLERK</i>	<i>Candidate: C. 3</i>
<i>Post 5: COUNTER CLERK / TELLER</i>	<i>Candidate: C. 5</i>

The graph of the evolution of the best individual in each generation is displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The results obtained from this work fall into two clusters. The first consists of the formulation of a staff selection model that could be adapted to the problem under consideration. The second has to do with the establishment of a specific procedure.

In addition, as a proposal for future work, this research has backed the interest in using natural linguistic operators with the aim of handling linguistic information without having to transform it into a semantic representation [HERRERA AND HERRERA-VIEDMA, 1997].

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